

Married Lives in Mahesh Dattani's 'Bravely Fought the Queen'

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Abstract:

In a rapidly changing world, India too has embraced transformation. The socio-economic and political conditions of India have changed in the twenty-first centuries. Because of this, the institutions like family, education, law and marriage have also undergone changes. The present paper discusses and describes the disturbed married lives of Trivedi family in Mahesh Dattani's 'Bravely Fought The Queen' (1991). Trivedi family lives in suburb of Bangalore, Karnataka, India. The husband-wife relationship in any literary piece stands in complex relationship with the contemporary familial issues of the time. Therefore, the present research paper contributes us to understand changing socio-economic and cultural problems that affect and pressurize the married life and husband-wife relationships in Indian context. This paper also focuses on successful and unsuccessful married relationships and traces its reasons being so.

Keywords: Transformation, Married Relationship, Context, Complex Relationships, Inseparable.

Marriage is one of the most meaningful institutions in human society. It is a sacred bond between two individuals who promise to support, respect, and care for each other throughout their lives. Married life plays an important role in shaping individuals, families, and society as a whole. Married life is something that is inseparable from the structure of Indian society. According to sociologies, the family in our country is complete when marriage takes place there through proper wedding ceremonies. Marriage is basically significant to society because it is the basic principle of the family and the basic building block of society. It brings significant stability and meaning to human relationships. It remains the ideal for the raising of children. It plays an important role in transmitting culture and civilization to future generations. Marriage is not merely a private contract, but a social institution of great public

value. As social science research and government surveys increasingly show, the decay in marriage since the 1960s has been accompanied by a rise in a number of serious social problems.

Mahesh Dattani is the first Indian playwright in English to be awarded the Sahitya Akademi Award in 1998, for his wonderful work *Final Solutions and Other Plays*. Dattani was born in Bangalore on 7th August, 1958. Though, his parents originally belonged to Porbandar of Gujarat. They have migrated to Bombay for business purpose and eventually settled in Bangalore where he found an opportunity of watching Gujarati and Kannada plays in the company of his parents and sisters. Dattani took his education from Baldwin High School and St. Joseph College of Arts and Science, Bangalore.

Mahesh Dattani's *Bravely Fought The Queen* (1991), is a stage play in three acts. It is a typical Indian family play which portrays the life

of the middle class family. The action of the play seems to be taking place in the era of 1990s. The married life in this play passes through different stages. All the three couples in the play are not satisfied in their lives. In our culture, marriage symbolizes not just the sacred union of two individuals, but of the coming together of two families and extended families as well. The play describes three married couples who form the core of the play. In this play Dolly and Alka two sisters married with Jiten and Nitin Trivedi brothers respectively. Shridhar and Lalitha is the third married couple in the play. However, there are other characters who contribute to the central action of the play. These characters are: Baa, mother of Jiten and Nitin Trivedi, Praful, brother of Dolly and Alka, Daksha, only girl of Jiten and Dolly, Kanhaiya the cook, an old lady, watchman, an auto driver and dead husband of Baa.

The relationship of Dolly–Jiten and Alka–Nitin occupies the central position in the discussion of the married life portrayed in the play. It brings forth many social, cultural and familial issues which are very significant in contemporary Indian family life. Dattani has presented Jiten as a dominant advocate of patriarchy. He does not respect his wife in fact any female characters in the play.

Married Life: Jiten and Dolly:

The play is composed in three acts. The *Act- I* called *The Women* elaborates all females in the play. All the women in the play except Lalitha are disappointed in their married life. Marriage of Dolly and Jiten is going through different stages. He behaves very rudely not only with his wife but with Alka and Lalitha all the same his mother Baa. It seems that the problem of fund raising for the Re Va Tee ad campaign disturbs him and his brother Nitin. Due to the tension of this they ill-treat their wife at home. Jiten is a misogynist whose attitude towards women is biased and has

no sensibility for them. He has lack of genuine feelings for his wife is the drawback of his personality as a man.

Jiten and Dolly are united in holy relationship called marriage but their relationship completely failed to achieve an ideal married life in society. As a husband he does not respect Dolly. She is constricted to four walls at home as in our Indian society wives are considered as servants at home mostly. She is not allowed to look in to the professional life of Jiten. She is not taken out of four walls to take part in various social activities. She does not get company of her husband who is brutal. She is rarely taken out. At the beginning of the play, both sisters are told to take out but the plan is cancelled. Their married life of sixteen years is crushed due to the nature of Jiten. At the end of the play, it is shown by the playwright that Dolly is courageous. She shows courage against her husband Jiten. She says;

Jiten: What's the matter with you ? I'm not throwing you out!

Dolly: No. You won't. You can't. (p.93)

Marriage as partnership should be balanced. The married life of Jiten and Dolly is spoiled and it is failure in consideration of our culture and law. She is going to accept injustice inactively by her husband. What is the output of this married life? At the end of the play she regains her female spirit and challenges her husband. She reminds him of his cruel behaviour with her fifteen years back when she was kicked in stomach by the orders of Baa. He gets convinced of his injustice with wife and daughter and starts crying. This married relationship has dark past of brutality, hatred, injustice and dominance takes positive turn in the end.

Married Life: Nitin and Alka:

Married Life of Nitin and Alka also occupies an important place in the play. Nitin is homosexual character in the play. Homosexuality

is an invisible issue in India. Nitin has sexual relationship with Praful, his brother-in-law. The importance of marriage has been identified for different reasons such as: it legitimizes the living together of two people of opposite sex through social and legal sanction; it legitimizes child birth in which nurturing children becomes the responsibility of both husband and wife. As Nitin is homosexual this is the basic reason behind the futile married life of Alka and Nitin.

Nitin further in the play develops this relationship with the auto rickshaw driver. They meet in the office at night as well as at his house. He is aware about his incompetency yet he tries to prove his manliness. He hides his sexual identity as 'homosexual.' This homosexuality of Nitin affects his married life i.e. his wife Alka. This couple still doesn't have a child after many years of their marriage. There is no satisfaction in the married life of a woman until she gives birth to a child. Nitin had no wish to marry with Alka so he blames about this to Praful. She gets troubled by her husband, as he has forced her to leave his home for three months because of insulting Baa. Because of this she feels isolated and to kill her isolation she becomes boozier. She has no child, she gets bad treatment from Jiten and Baa also. Alka admits that she is not an ideal housewife.

Alka is tortured by her mother-in-law for not having a child after many years of their marriage. The following dialogues show this;

Alka: You know why I can't have children. You won't let me. That's why!

Baa: What are you saying?

Alka: You won't let us!

Baa : You are mad, mad, mad !

Alka : You won't let us ! You want him to hate me!(p.64)

Nitin has strong hatred for praful because he is deceived by him. Baa is unhappy with Alka. Nitin was told in the past to get married with Alka so that both Nitin and Praful could continue

their relationship. Praful forced Alka to get married with Nitin as Praful disallowed Alka's intimacy for her college mate. Thus, this is how the married life of Alka is spoiled because of her husband.

Married Life: Shridhar and Lalitha:

The dramatist portrays the third married couple exact opposite to earlier married relationships of Trivedi family. Shridhar is an ideal husband as he treats his wife and understands her. He is an employee of Trivedi brothers. Actually, this is new couple having poor background living in Bangalore. This married life is marked by intimacy, mutual love and respect for one another. Lalitha has professional life who works occasionally as journalist. Her life is not restricted to four walls like other married women in the play. Two wives in the play are confined to traditional household duties. Shridhar takes her out and both are saving for their flat. Shridhar's relationship is very good to that of Jiten and Nitin Trivedi. Lalitha has a better position in the play than Dolly and Alka or Baa. She has a freedom to enjoy outside life. She has her side to decide whether they should have children or not.

As a wife of Shridhar she does not suffer but she suffers from society. Shridhar is an ideal husband of Lalitha who is more protective. He does not like insulted by Jiten even if he works for him. When Lalitha requests Dolly to go home at the same time Jiten talks rudely;

Lalitha: Please, Dolly. Could you help us go home?

Alka: Jiten, drop them at an auto stand.

Lalitha: Yes, please. It's getting late and.....

Jiten: (to Lalitha). Just shut up!

Shridhar: That's no way to talk to a lady. (p.86)

The above dialogue of Shridhar shows that he is protective as in married life every

husband must be like him. Shridhar's care of Lalitha makes him an adorable husband and likable character. He understands her sensibility which is absent in Jiten and Nitin. This relationship is depicted as an ideal relationship in the play. The concept of marriage a sort of husband-wife relationship is a responsible one-to-one unit of society-evolved a unique human family system. It's essential components were intercourse, procreation of children and living together with mutual obligations and responsibilities to the care of offspring. It seems that this care and awareness of other issues are taken in to mind by Shridhar and Lalitha.

Married Life of Baa:

The married life of Baa, mother of Jiten and Nitin can not be neglected as it highlights the domestic violence. Baa is an ailing mother of Trivedi brothers with grey hair and a white sari. Through a series of flashbacks in the play, we know that her past is very tragic and she is the victim of her husband after marriage. Baa has not forgotten her past married life which is marked by physical torture. The reminiscences of her past still do not allow her to live a peaceful life. The fear of her husband is still in her mind. She still fears of her husband's memories. She has been a typical mother-in-law who is very much prejudiced towards her daughters-in-law. The husband of Baa was violent and cruel who prevented her from singing. She desires love, support and understanding from her sons. The institution of marriage gives respectability to women, enhances their personal happiness and welfare, and provides family support and companionship.

Now a day, family is becoming just an individualistic conjugal family, not even aware of its roots. From times immemorial, Hindus have tried to idealize and sanctify the institution of marriage as no other civil society has done so far.

Conjugal fidelity is regarded as the supreme virtue of a woman and it is this character that has protected the Hindu race and Hindu religion down the ages. Purity of the soil and the seed—the sperm and the ovum—alone contributes to the purity of a race and it is with this end in view that so much stress has been laid in our scriptures on the chastity and fidelity of women.

Thus, the discussion of married relationships in the play puts forth many socio-cultural and familial issues. Married life contributes to social and economic stability. Couples work together to achieve financial security and common goals. Cooperation and teamwork help them overcome challenges and build a better future. However, a successful married life depends on understanding, communication, trust, and patience. In conclusion, married life is important because it provides love, companionship, security, and a sense of belonging. When based on mutual respect and understanding, marriage becomes a strong foundation for a happy life and a healthy society. The playwright shows that, in the past it is seen that the married life was happy and satisfactory. As the passage of time it goes on changing. Dattani has aptly portrayed this relationship of contemporary Indian society in his play.

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